

Development and effectivity of *Solanum sisymbriifolium* against potato cyst nematode under field conditions in soils from the southern atlantic area

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ABSTRACT

Potato cyst nematodes (PCNs), belonging to the genus *Globodera* spp., are spread worldwide constituting a problem of concern as they can cause considerable losses in crop yields. An alternative to the application of common pesticides is the use of trap crops, that promote the hatching of second-stage juvenile cysts without supporting the feeding and reproduction of these nematodes. For this purpose, in recent years, there has been growing attention to the use of *Solanum sisymbriifolium* as a biopesticide. In this study, we focused on looking for the best conditions to grow this trap crop under field conditions, contrary to previous studies developed in pots under controlled conditions. Various management strategies, including sowing date and depth, irrigation and soil compaction, to grow *S. sisymbriifolium* in acid sandy soils (pH 4.3–5.5) have been evaluated. In addition, the efficiency of *S. sisymbriifolium* was tested under field conditions in three PCN-infested plots. The results indicate that the best conditions for *S. sisymbriifolium* cropping in South Atlantic latitudes included sowing dates in July and August at 10–15 cm depth, with irrigation and soil compaction after sowing. Under these conditions, a 77%–89% decrease in PCNs was observed with a high initial number of cysts (93–160 per 100g), and even some subplots showed a 100% reduction when the initial number of cysts was low (15–52 per 100g). Therefore, *S. sisymbriifolium* could be an interesting substitute for unspecific chemical nematicides in potato crops to promote sustainable agriculture.

1. Introduction

The production of potatoes can be threatened by the presence of very thin worms in the soil of the *Globodera* spp. Genus. These worms are also known as potato cyst nematodes (PCNs) and can cause notable damage and losses in crop yields. Crop yields can be reduced from 19% to 80%, depending on soil infestation severity and cultivar. Notably, approximately 9% of worldwide potato losses are caused by PCNs (Turner and Subbotin, 2013). Given their potential ability to cause severe losses in crop yields, a European Directive has legislated the detection, prevention and control of this plague (E.C., 2007). In worst cases, with more than 50 viable cysts per 100 g of soil, potato crops can be restricted for six years owing to mandatory quarantine.

The infection of potato crops begins with the presence of second-stage juvenile (J2) cysts in the soil, which can be latent for years

without a host plant (Turner, 1996; Perry, 2002). When the climate conditions are favourable, as in spring and summer, the root exudates of the host plant are liberated stimulating the hatching of J2 cysts. The nematodes enter through the root tips of the plant and establish the feeding site in the roots (syncytium), finishing in the following cycle stages (Scholte and Vos, 2000; Varandas et al., 2020; Kud et al., 2022). Some disease symptoms include delayed plant development, yellow leaves, decreased photosynthetic rate or circular patches in the canopy, which are not easy to identify (Nicol et al., 2011).

There are various strategies for controlling PCNs, but one of the most common is using nematicides. However, the demands of the global economy for more sustainable agriculture are increasingly restricting chemical pesticides, as included in the Farm to Fork Strategy of the European Union (E.U., 2020). For this reason, different alternatives have emerged, including resistant cultivars, crop rotation with no-host plants

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or biological alternatives such as trap crops (Varandas et al., 2020). Trap crops include some plants of the Solanaceae family, which have shown the ability to produce hatching agents guaranteeing resistance to PCNs (Scholte, 2000a,b; Timmermans et al., 2006).

In this sense, the high potential of *Solanum sisymbriifolium* (litchi tomato) as an effective trap crop against PCNs has been reported in some studies (Scholte, 2000a,b; Scholte and Vos, 2000). Being a distant relative of tomatoes and potatoes, this plant stimulates the hatching of *Globodera* spp. Eggs without promoting nematode reproduction, allowing it to be used as a trap crop (Scholte and Vos, 2000). As soon as the nematodes penetrate the plant and establish the feeding site, the early stages of development are rapidly inhibited (Crawley et al., 2014; Kooliyottil et al., 2016). PCN infestation reduction using this crop has been reported in some studies, with percentages varying from 52% to 77% (Scholte and Vos, 2000; Timmermans et al., 2006), depending on the severity of soil infestation, growth duration, or both. Dandurand and Knudsen (2016) and Mhatre et al. (2021) obtained a 99% reduction in *Globodera pallida* using pot experiments. Although *S. sisymbriifolium* is native to South America, it grows well under temperate climates, as the present study area, and is resistant to night frosts in autumn (Scholte, 2000a,b).

Most studies on the use of *S. sisymbriifolium* against PCN infestation have been performed in pots filled with either or both artificial and sterilised soils in greenhouse-controlled conditions (Scholte, 2000a,b; Timmermans et al., 2006; Dias et al., 2012; Dandurand and Knudsen, 2016; Dandurand et al., 2019; Fatemy and Ahmarimoghadam, 2019; Mhatre et al., 2021; Pillai and Dandurand, 2021). However, only two studies have included field experiments (Scholte and Vos, 2000; Timmermans et al., 2007a). These two studies focused only on sowing dates, and both were performed in Central Atlantic European latitudes. For this reason, in this study, we assessed the more suitable field conditions for optimum *S. sisymbriifolium* development in South Atlantic European latitudes, considering not only the planting date but also sowing depth, irrigation and soil compaction after sowing. The specific objectives are: 1) To know the best conditions for *S. sisymbriifolium* emergence and

development; and 2) To test the capacity of this trap crop to reduce nematode cyst populations in the soil before potato cropping, both for Central Atlantic European latitudes.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

The study area is located in Galicia (Northwest Spain) in the Atlantic biogeographical region of Europe (Fig. 1). This region's climate is characterised by mild temperatures and high rainfall and is influenced by western winds. Two different experiments were conducted in four plots in Sandiás, Piñeira Seca (2 plots, Piñeira 1 and 2) and Bustelo (Xinzo de Limia, Ourense). The experiments are described in the following sections.

2.2. Experimental procedure

2.2.1. Analyses of the best conditions for *S. sisymbriifolium* emergence and development

The first field experiment was developed in 2021 to test different crop management options for optimising the emergence and development of *S. sisymbriifolium*. It was conducted over an experimental area of 5000 m² in Sandiás (Ourense), with the coordinates 42° 6' 5.16" N, 7° 43' 31.53" W. The experiment plot was considered uniform in soil characteristics with 80% sand content, 5% organic matter (OM) and a pH (measured in water, pH_w) of 5.0.

Crop planting date and depth of sowing were evaluated together with two auxiliary parameters (soil compaction and irrigation). The design followed the parameters described in Fig. 2. The chosen crop plantation dates were the 4th and 28th of June. *Solanum sisymbriifolium* seeds were sown at a rate of 20 kg per ha at three different depths: 5, 10 and 15 cm. Half of the plot was compacted with a roller while the other half was not, and the same applies to irrigation. In both sowing dates and the three depths, the soil moisture was around 20%.

Fig. 1. Location of the study area (black circle) in the Atlantic biogeographical regions of Europe (2016) (E.E.A., 2017).

Fig. 2. Design of the *S. sisymbriifolium* experimental plot. Combinations of compaction, irrigation, sowing depth and date were tested.

Plants were collected on the 15th of September, specifically 103 and 79 days after the crop planting dates. From each experiment, three subsamples were taken at 1 m² each, and the number of plants and the crop yield were measured.

2.2.2. Testing *S. sisymbriifolium* efficiency against PCNs under field conditions

After the first experiment, in which the optimum conditions for *S. sisymbriifolium* growth in the studied area were known, a second experiment was developed in another three plots (Table 1) in 2022 to see the efficiency of *S. sisymbriifolium* as a trap crop against PCNs under field conditions. All the experiments were developed in plots authorised by the farmers where periodic control tests detected high levels of PCNs. The three plots were located in Piñeira Seca (Piñeira 1 and 2) and Bustelo da Veiga (Bustelo), with extensions of approximately 4000, 3600 and 1000 m², respectively. In the Bustelo plot, half was planted with *S. sisymbriifolium* and half grew wheat planted during autumn 2021. The main soil characteristics of the three plots are shown in Table 1. pH_w , measured in a ratio of 1:5, was slightly acidic for the three plots, varying between 4.3 and 5.5. The highest OM content was found in Bustelo (6.7%) and the lowest in Piñeira 2 (4.0%). Phosphorous extracted using the Olsen method was similar in the three soils (118–164 mg kg⁻¹). Effective cation exchange capacity was practically the same for the three soils (approximately 3.8 cmolc kg⁻¹), with the highest exchangeable Ca found in Piñeira 2 (2 cmolc kg⁻¹).

S. sisymbriifolium seeds were planted on the 8th of July for Piñeira 1 and 2 and on the 10th of July for Bustelo. The seeds were sown at a dose of 20 kg per ha at a depth of 15 cm. In Bustelo, the soil was mechanically compacted after seed plantation. In the case of Piñeira 1, the soil was harrowed before sowing, and a precipitation event compacted the soil just after sowing. In Piñeira 2, the precipitations dispersed the seeds, making the distribution irregular in the plot. No herbicides or fertilisers were applied in any plot during plant development, but insecticides

Table 1
Principal soil characteristics of the three plots used in the different experiments.

	^a pH _w	^b OM	^c P Olsen	^d Ca _{ex}	Mg _{ex}	K _{ex}	Na _{ex}	^e CECe
		%	mg kg ⁻¹	cmolc kg ⁻¹				
Piñeira 1	4.8	4.9	164	0.93	0.35	1.28	1.31	3.87
Bustelo	4.3	6.7	118	1.53	0.43	0.85	0.94	3.76
Piñeira 2	5.5	4.0	153	2.04	0.43	0.81	0.61	3.88

^a pH_w: water pH in the soil at a ratio 1:5.

^b OM: organic matter calcined at 450 °C during 4 h.

^c P Olsen: assimilable phosphorous extracted by the Olsen method.

^d Ca_{ex}, Mg_{ex}, K_{ex}, Na_{ex}: exchangeable cations with NH₄Cl 1M.

^e CECe: effective cation exchange capacity.

were used to control beetles. Finally, *S. sisymbriifolium* plants were buried in the plots on the 30th of September (84 days) in Piñeira 1, the 15th of September in Piñeira 2 (69 days) and the 10th of October (92 days) in Bustelo. Trap plants were plated after biannual potato–wheat crop rotation: potato cv Agria (2021), winter wheat (2020) and potato cv Kennebec (2019) for Piñeira 1; potato cv Agria (2019), winter wheat (2020) and potato cv Agria (2021) for Piñeira 2; spring wheat (2021), potato cv Agria (2020) and spring wheat (2019) for Bustelo.

Soil samples were randomly collected at eight points in Piñeira 1 and Bustelo and six points in Piñeira 2 before sowing and after burying *S. sisymbriifolium* to know the initial (P_i) and final (P_f) counting of PCN cysts. The initial sampling was made just the day before the sowing of *S. sisymbriifolium*, specifically on the 8th of July for Piñeira 1 and 2 and the 9th of July (2022) for Bustelo. The final PCN cyst sampling was done on the 29th of November for both Piñeira 1 and Bustelo and on the 25th of November for Piñeira 2, approximately 2 months after burying *S. sisymbriifolium*. In the Bustelo sub-plot not sowed with *S. sisymbriifolium*, soil samples were taken at the same time as the plot sowed in eight points. The reproduction factor (RF) was estimated as P_f/P_i.

2.3. Monitoring of weather conditions during field trials

In 2021, daily meteorological data were recorded using an autonomous weather station (i-METOS, iMETOS ® 3.3, Pessl Instruments, Weiz, Austria) placed near (300 m) the experimental plot in Sandiás (Ourense). The selected daily meteorological factors were temperature (minimum [minT], maximum [maxT] and mean [meanT], °C), soil moisture (soil moisture [soil moisture], kPa) and total rainfall (rain [rain], mm). The soil moisture sensor measures the degree of water retention in the soil. This measurement is based on the principle that water is held in the soil by the attractive forces between water molecules and the soil.

The following year (2022), this weather station was used to measure the weather conditions in the experimental plot of Bustelo (7 km far away). Another weather station (Cesens® mini) was installed in Piñeira Seca (1 km away from the two experimental plots, Piñeira 1 and 2). The selected daily meteorological factors were temperature (mean [meanT], °C) and total rain (rain [rain], mm).

The Growing Degree Days (GDD) model was calculated according to the proposal of Franc et al. (1988), with a base temperature of 7 °C, as shown in the following equations:

$$GDDs = \frac{\max T + \min T}{2} - \text{baseT} \text{ If } \frac{\max T + \min T}{2} - \text{baseT} \geq 0$$

$$GDDs = 0 \text{ If } \frac{\max T + \min T}{2} - \text{baseT} < 0$$

2.3.1. Phenological stages

To observe the establishment of the crop at two different sowing dates, different phenological stages were determined. In 2021, the period from sowing to emergence was observed at each sowing date in the test plot. Another period was also studied between 50% and 70% of the emergence and beginning of flowering. Finally, the entire crop cycle was considered until the 15th of September when the plants were harvested. In 2022, periods from sowing to 50% of emergence, from 50% of emergence to the beginning of flowering and the total growing season from sowing to cutting of the plants were considered in the farmer's trial plots.

2.4. PCN cyst analyses

Each plot of experiment 2 was divided into different sub-plots: eight in Bustelo (both sown and not sown), eight in Piñeira 1 and six in Piñeira 2. On each sub-plot, 20 points were taken randomly at a depth of 10 cm,

mixed and homogenised.

Once in the laboratory, soil samples were air-dried at 30 °C until they reached constant humidity and then sieved through a 2-mm mesh size. After that, two extractions were made before cyst counting. First, 100 g of soil is introduced in the upper part of the Fenwick can. Soil particles settle at the bottom of the can while the nematode cysts surpass the edge of the can and are collected in a 0.25-mm sieve. In the second extraction, following the Seinhorst method, the sample is introduced in a flask filled with ethanol, and the cysts are separated by buoyancy. In both cases, the nematode cyst samples are collected using filter paper for counting. On one hand, *Globodera* spp. Cysts in 100 g of soil are counted using a binocular stereomicroscopic magnifier based on their morphology. Then, for juveniles and larvae, samples are introduced in an Eppendorf tube and crushed using a punch. Finally, the sample is placed in a McMaster counting chamber and counted using a microscope (Viaene et al., 2020; EPPO, 2022).

2.5. Statistical analyses

A Kruskal–Wallis test was conducted to elucidate if there were statistical differences in the emergence and growth of *S. sisymbriifolium* depending on the different crop parameters (sowing date and depth, soil compaction and irrigation). A paired *t*-test (conducted after checking data normality using the Shapiro–Wilk test) was also applied to observe statistically significant differences between the P_i and P_f cyst nematode egg densities in the three studied plots and in the control not sowed with *S. sisymbriifolium*. These analyses were done using IBM SPSS Statistics 25.0.

3. Results

3.1. Sowing management for *S. sisymbriifolium* emergence and growth

Considering the GDDs accumulated in each growing season, the differences were small: 377.5 GDDs accumulated in the growing season of the first sowing date (4th of June), and 307.0 GDDs accumulated in the second sowing date (28th of June) (Table 2). Compared with the second sowing date, the first growing season was the wettest. A total of 180 mm of rain accumulated in the first full crop season compared with 117 mm in the second full crop season (Table 2). On the second sowing date, temperatures were slightly higher, and rainfall occurred but with less water (Table 2).

At the beginning of June, when the first plot was sowed, there was a prolonged period of rain that flooded the land (Fig. 3). In the emergence period of the first sowing date considered as 17 days elapsed from sowing, the mean temperature reached almost 17 °C, quite higher than the mean temperature of 17 days (16.2 °C) after sowing in the second date. Maximum temperatures reached 25.2 °C on the first sowing date, and the minimum temperature was under 9 °C. Compared with the first date, the second date reached higher minimum temperatures (9.1 °C) and lower maximum temperatures (23.7 °C). Relative humidity did not show differences between both sowing dates. It rained 60.4 mm in the first 17 days after the first sowing date compared with only 10.4 mm at the second sowing date.

In general, the emergence of plants sown on the first date was

Table 2

Mean weather parameters considering the phenological stages of *S. sisymbriifolium* and two sowing dates for the whole crop season.

Sowing date	meanT (°C)	maxT (°C)	minT (°C)	Rain (mm)	Soil moisture (kPa)	GDDs (units)
4 th June	17.5	25.8	9.8	181.2	100.0	377.5
28 th June	17.9	26.3	10.2	117.4	127.3	307.0

Fig. 3. Weather conditions during two different sowing dates of *S. sisymbriifolium* in Sandiás. A) General view of weather conditions and main phenological stages of *S. sisymbriifolium* including both sowing dates. B) Weather conditions and phenological development of *S. sisymbriifolium* during first month after sowing (first sowing date, 4th June). C) Weather conditions and phenological development of *S. sisymbriifolium* during first month after sowing (second sowing date, 28th June).

delayed until the last days of August (Fig. 3). The yield obtained after 103 days of development (first sowing date) was not significant for the sowing depths of 5 and 15 cm, independently of soil compaction and irrigation parameters. The highest yields were obtained for the 10-cm sowing depth plants, supported by the statistical differences found after a Kruskal–Wallis test following sowing depth (H = 6.873; r = 0.009). It was especially noticeable for the combination of irrigated and

non-compacted plots. In these sub-samples, the mean value of collected plants was 119, and the mean yield was 4169 g (Table 3). In contrast, the plants of the second sowing date (28th June) emerged around the 15th of July. In this case, they had 79 days for the development (until the 15th of September), reflected in the higher number of plants and yields obtained than the plants sowed on the first date. The production of plants at the sowing depth of 5 cm was not significant in all the cases (Table 4). The highest number of individual plants was obtained for the 15 cm–not irrigated–compacted combination, with a mean value of three sub-samples of 135 and an average yield of 4440 g. However, higher yields were obtained for the plants sowed at the same depth (15 cm) and compacted but with irrigation (5393 g). This difference between irrigated (67 g) and non-irrigated plants (33 g) is noticeable in the mean weight obtained for each plant. We found statistical differences after a Kruskal–Wallis test between irrigated and non-irrigated *S. sisymbriifolium* crops, both for n° plants ($H = 7.074$; $r = 0.008$) and yields ($H = 9.795$; $r = 0.002$).

3.2. Development of *S. sisymbriifolium* under real farms and effects on PCN development

3.2.1. Weather conditions during phenological development of *S. sisymbriifolium*

In 2022, crop establishment was rapid. In the two areas (Piñeira and Bustelo), emergence occurred between 11 and 14 days after sowing, with an accumulation of between 20 and 31 GDDs (Table 5). The temperature did not vary during this period in either site, but rainfall was more abundant in Bustelo than in Piñeira, without large amounts of water being recorded. To start flowering, the plants in both areas needed between 95 and 114 GDDs, which accumulated within 26 and 33 days after plant emergence, respectively. Temperature was similar in both sites but rainfall was higher at Piñeira (67.4 mm) than Bustelo (4.6 mm). Overall, the crop cycle took 72 days on average to complete in both areas, requiring between 209 and 245 GDDs (Table 5).

3.2.2. Effect on PCN development

The quantity of P_1 before the *S. sisymbriifolium* plantation in Bustelo ranged from 93 to 189 cysts/100 g and 72–147 cysts/100 g in sub-plots planted and not planted with the trap crop, respectively. Lower initial values were found in Piñeira 1, with P_1 varying from 15 to 52 cysts/100 g. In Piñeira 2, the P_1 was 71–219 cysts/100 g (Table 6). Differences between the P_1 and P_f n° cysts per 100 g of soil in plots with *S. sisymbriifolium* crop were significant in the three plots with the trap crop [Bustelo ($t = 8.691$; $p < 0.001$), Piñeira 1 ($t = 5.923$; $p < 0.001$) and Piñeira 2 ($t = 2.791$; $p = 0.038$)] (Table 6/Fig. 6a–b and c), but also for the sub-plot not sowed with it ($t = 7.195$; $p < 0.001$) (Table 7/Fig. 6d), suggesting a seasonal reduction in the number of cysts. However, the magnitude of the reductions was very different for the different

plots (Fig. 6). The average percentage reduction of cysts in the P_f for Bustelo and Piñeira 1 after 13 and 12 weeks of *S. sisymbriifolium* growth was 77% and 89%, respectively. In the Piñeira 1 plot, some of the points sampled achieved complete PCN elimination, with a percentage reduction of 100% (Table 6). In the case of Piñeira 2, the plot with the highest PCN P_i , the average percentage reduction was 29%, much less than that in the other two plots. This may have been due to an incorrect germination of *S. sisymbriifolium* in this plot, resulting in poor plant growth (Fig. 5c) compared with the other two locations. These results highlight the importance of adequate sowing to achieve high efficiency in reducing cyst nematodes. Considerably lower reductions of PCN cysts were found in a nearby plot without *S. sisymbriifolium*, with the common rotation potato–wheat–potato. In this case, the percentage reduction regarding the P_i of PCN cysts varied at 13%–20% in the sub-plot not sowed with the trap crop (Table 7).

4. Discussion

Correctly managing the *S. sisymbriifolium* crop is the key to high effectiveness against PCNs. Environmental conditions seem to be the determining factor for the good establishment and development of *S. sisymbriifolium* plants. After this experiment, we noticed that the differences in plant germination and development between the first and second sowing dates may be attributed to the intense and continuous rainfall during the germination period on the first sowing date with lower temperatures. Under these conditions, the plants grew weak and could not develop and compete with other weeds (Fig. 4). The earliest sowing date (4th June) did not reach a good development. During this period, the temperature was variable and did not reach a maximum of 16 °C. However, in 2022, sowing was conducted between the 8th and 10th of July with average temperatures of 23 °C, allowing a correct development of the crop (Fig. 5a and b). Therefore, germination and emergence are processes negatively affected by low temperatures. Although there are few references in the literature on the environmental conditions suitable for the development of *S. sisymbriifolium*, the same conclusions were published by Timmermans et al. (2007a,b), who found that temperatures below 12 °C cause slow and irregular emergence. This is because this temperature is close to the base temperature observed for crops in warmer ecosystems, such as 6 °C–9.5 °C for rice (Sie et al., 1998) and 10 °C for most maize cultivars (Ruiz et al., 1998). They also demonstrated that planting before June did not improve crop growth and yields. Thus, in our climate region, the successful emergence and development of the trap crop is achieved when soil temperatures are higher than 10 °C (Fig. 3), which is the usual base temperature for several crops in temperate and warm regions, and preferably between July and August when it is easier to reach ideal temperatures constantly. This conclusion also supports the premise of Timmermans et al. (2007a, b) to introduce the planting date of this crop after the cereal harvest of

Table 3

Number of plants and yields obtained for the first sowing date (4th June) at the different conditions established. Each subsample is referred to as 1 m².

4 th June			Subsample 1		Subsample 2		Subsample 3	
Irrigation	Compaction	Sowing depth cm	n° plants	yield g	n° plants	yield g	n° plants	yield g
Not irrigated	Compacted	5	^a ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Not irrigated	Not compacted	5	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Not irrigated	Compacted	10	10	700	9	710	15	820
Not irrigated	Not compacted	10	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Not irrigated	Compacted	15	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Not irrigated	Not compacted	15	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Irrigated	Compacted	5	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Irrigated	Not compacted	5	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Irrigated	Compacted	10	78	2200	85	2350	70	2150
Irrigated	Not compacted	10	113	4350	109	3598	136	4560
Irrigated	Compacted	15	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Irrigated	Not compacted	15	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

^a Not significant.

Table 4

Number of plants and yields obtained for the second sowing date (28th June) at the different conditions established. Each subsample is referred to as 1 m².

28 th June			Subsample 1		Subsample 2		Subsample 3	
Irrigation	Compaction	Sowing depth cm	n° plants	yield g	n° plants	yield g	n° plants	yield g
Not irrigated	Compacted	5	^a ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Not irrigated	Not compacted	5	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Not irrigated	Compacted	10	32	2200	40	2600	35	2210
Not irrigated	Not compacted	10	35	1500	28	1680	30	1480
Not irrigated	Compacted	15	126	4100	149	5020	130	4200
Not irrigated	Not compacted	15	55	2000	60	2100	64	2300
Irrigated	Compacted	5	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Irrigated	Not compacted	5	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Irrigated	Compacted	10	113	4350	109	3598	136	4560
Irrigated	Not compacted	10	78	2200	80	2400	64	2350
Irrigated	Compacted	15	77	5200	80	5450	86	5530
Irrigated	Not compacted	15	44	4100	50	4600	35	3900

^a Not significant.

Table 5

Weather conditions recorded during the phenological development of *S. sisymbriifolium* in the two experimental sites in 2022: Bustelo (B) and Piñeira (P).

	B				P			
	No. days	meanT	Rain	GDDs	No. days	meanT	Rain	GDDs
Sowing - 50% emergence	11	23.2	36.6	30.9	14	23.2	28.8	19.8
50% emergence - Onset flowering	26	21.8	4.6	113.6	33	20.5	67.4	94.8
Full crop season	74	20.4	51.0	244.5	70	20.2	120.6	208.8

Table 6

Initial egg density (Pi), final egg density (Pf) per 100 g of soil and Reproduction Factor (RF) in the three plots studied, Bustelo (B), Piñeira 1 (P) and Piñeira 2 (C).

Subplot	Pi	Pf	RF
1B	104 ± 8	31 ± 3	0.30
2B	93 ± 15	34 ± 8	0.37
3B	132 ± 17	39 ± 10	0.30
4B	189 ± 8	33 ± 6	0.17
5B	160 ± 22	25 ± 6	0.16
6B	151 ± 24	22 ± 5	0.15
7B	144 ± 24	34 ± 8	0.24
8B	98 ± 12	19 ± 1	0.19
1P	43 ± 12	5 ± 1	0.12
2P	13 ± 3	4 ± 1	0.31
3P	32 ± 6	8 ± 2	0.25
4P	49 ± 6	5 ± 0	0.10
5P	52 ± 12	0 ± 0	0.00
6P	47 ± 10	0 ± 0	0.00
7P	15 ± 4	0 ± 0	0.00
8P	34 ± 8	3 ± 1	0.09
1C	85 ± 8	31 ± 7	0.36
2C	71 ± 11	84 ± 16	1.18
3C	187 ± 20	142 ± 11	0.76
4C	211 ± 13	122 ± 18	0.58
5C	219 ± 15	148 ± 9	0.68
6C	90 ± 8	78 ± 1	0.87

Table 7

Initial egg density (Pi), final egg density (Pf) per 100 g of soil and Reproduction Factor (RF) in a plot located in the study area but without *S. sisymbriifolium*.

Subplot	Pi	Pf	RF
1D	123 ± 12	102 ± 8	0,83
2D	90 ± 12	78 ± 4	0,87
3D	96 ± 13	81 ± 11	0,85
4D	133 ± 19	114 ± 18	0,86
5D	147 ± 16	117 ± 13	0,80
6D	107 ± 4	91 ± 2	0,85
7D	87 ± 13	76 ± 10	0,87
8D	72 ± 9	62 ± 8	0,86

Fig. 4. Weeds between *S. sisymbriifolium* plants.

the same year. Although it is necessary to conduct further simulations of sowing dates in this crop to have an idea, for example, of using *S. sisymbriifolium* after commercial crops harvested during June or July, this sowing period is positive for the farmer as it does not replace any crop and occupies agricultural land that would be empty during the winter. This provides benefits of nematode reduction, nutrient fixation and use of trap crops as green manure without affecting traditional crop cycles. Therefore, this strategy can be a well-accepted strategy by potato farmers and a sustainable alternative to chemical nematicides in the South Atlantic biogeographical region.

Evaluating the effect of trap crops on PCN development is the other aim of this study. The results reached in two farmers' plots are somewhat higher than those obtained by Dandurand et al. (2019), who found a 50% reduction of PCN cysts compared with fallow treatment in different fields in the United States. They are also similar to the percentage reduction of Scholte and Vos (2000) in their field experiments in sandy and acidic soils (52%–77%). The Piñeira 1 and Bustelo plots have sandy acidic soils, favouring higher yields for *S. sisymbriifolium*. Generally, the highest percentages of reductions were found in the sub-plots with the lower initial number of cysts, which agrees with the results of

Fig. 5. *S. sisymbriifolium* development in the three plot studied: Bustelo (a), Piñeira 1 (b) and Piñeira 2 (c). Fig. 5d shows the effect of the water retention in compacted soil caused by the tractor wheels as they pass over the land, helping the seeds to germinate.

Scholte (2000a,b) who observed the highest percentages of PCN reduction in the least infested fields. Bustelo and Piñeira 1 RF values are somewhat higher than those obtained by Baker et al. (2023) in their pot experiments for the plant-parasitic nematode *Meloidogyne* spp. In field experiments, Bhatta et al. (2023) also obtained low values of RF for *G. pallida*, between 0.06 and 0.14. In addition, Fatemy and Ahmarimoghadam (2019) found RF values of 0.20 after 3 months of *S. sisymbriifolium* growing in pots for *Globodera rostochiensis*. Bhatta et al. (2023) also found no reproduction of *G. pallida* nematodes in *S. sisymbriifolium*, pointing out the suitability of this plant as a non-host crop. The significant reduction in PCN cysts can be due to the hatching effect that *S. sisymbriifolium* exerts on PCN J2 through the root exudates, as was demonstrated in field experiments in Portugal by Dias et al. (2017). The main compound responsible for J2 hatching seems to be the triterpenoid metabolite, solanoelepin A (SolA) since a positive correlation between *S. sisymbriifolium* hatching effect and SolA concentration was found by Guerrieri et al. (2021) in some cultivars of *S. sisymbriifolium*. Moreover, any *S. sisymbriifolium* cv. May be used for this purpose since several works have demonstrated the resistance of different cultivars to PCNs (Scholte, 2000a,b; Dias et al., 2017; Roberts and Stone, 1983). Timmermans et al. (2006) and Dandurand et al. (2019) also demonstrated the influence of the growth duration on the hatching of J2 from cysts, especially in field experiments, being considerably higher the longer the *S. sisymbriifolium* growth period becomes. In contrast to the field, in pot experiments, *S. sisymbriifolium* roots rapidly colonised all the containers due to a smaller distance between the roots and cysts, thus allowing faster hatching (Scholte, 2000a, b).

Overall, with the Atlantic climate conditions and acid sandy soil containing high amounts of OM, we have shown the best parameters for *S. sisymbriifolium* emergence and development. After testing different conditions of sowing date, sowing depth, irrigation and soil compaction, we conclude that the best combination for growing *S. sisymbriifolium* is planting with high mean temperatures (in July) at a depth of 10–15 cm, applying irrigation and compacting the soil after sowing with a roller. However, depending on the soil moisture, precipitation and sunlight, a

good number of plants and yields can also be obtained without irrigation and artificial soil compaction (Fig. 5d).

We have demonstrated the efficacy of *S. sisymbriifolium* for trapping PCNs (*Globodera* spp.), as shown by the high percentages of reduction in the plots studied. However, since a non-complete elimination of PCNs was obtained in all the plots, supplementary mechanisms could be included in future works, including the combination of *S. sisymbriifolium* with biocontrol agents such as seed meal extracts of other species (Baker et al., 2023; Roberts and Stone, 1983) or fungi (Dandurand and Knudsen, 2016). Despite its weed risk, *S. sisymbriifolium* is not only a useful crop for this purpose but also for its economic value in nutrition and traditional medicine (Biswas et al., 2023; Mhatre et al., 2022), a fact that is actually under investigation. Maybe, in the future, instead of the destruction of these invasive plants after using them for trapping PCNs in rotation with other crops, they could be used for obtaining additional economic income by the farmers, allowing them to recover part of the inversion for the establishment of *S. sisymbriifolium* crop. We have shown the ability of *S. sisymbriifolium* to considerably reduce the number of PCNs in one season when cropped in rotation with potatoes in field experiments at a relatively large scale. However, due to the limited number of studies, further investigations in other climates and with other soil characteristics are necessary to study the efficacy of *S. sisymbriifolium* in different latitudes.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Antía Gómez-Armesto: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Laura Meno:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Servando Álvarez-Pousa:** Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources. **David Fernández-Calviño:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition.

Fig. 6. Initial N°/cysts (Pi, green) and final N°/cysts (Pf, yellow) in the three plots studied: Bustelo (a; samples 1B–8B), Piñeira 1 (b; samples 1P–8P), Piñeira 2 (c; samples 1C–6C), and in a plot located in the same area without *S. sisymbriifolium* crop (d: samples 1D–8D). Bars indicate standard deviation (SD).

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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